

Blockchain and Federated-Learning empowered secure and trustworthy vehicular traffic

Banhirup Sengupta*, Souvik Sengupta†, Susham Nandi‡ and Anthony Simonet-Boulogne†

*Departament de Matemàtiques, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain

† iExec Blockchain Tech, France

‡ Liverpool John Moore University, United Kingdom

Email: *sengupta@mat.uab.cat †(souvik, anthony)@iex.ec, ‡S.Nandi@2022.ljmu.ac.uk

Abstract—Emergence of the autonomous and connected vehicles and modern vehicular networks improved the quality of the traditional transportation system. However, because of the increased usage of software and the development of wireless interfaces, vehicular networks, autonomous vehicles, and the overall transportation infrastructure are vulnerable to cyber-attacks. Intrusion detection mechanisms (IDM) can be easily tailored in response to the increasing attack surface. Deep learning algorithms have made tremendous progress in detecting such malicious attack traffic. On the other hand, Existing IDM requires network devices with high computational capabilities to continuously train and update complicated network models, which limits intrusion detection systems’ efficiency and defence potential due to restricted resources and late model updates. Therefore to address this issue, this paper proposes a cooperative intrusion detection mechanism that distributes the training model across dispersed edge devices (such as linked automobiles, autonomous vehicles and roadside units (RSU)). Furthermore, we used the distributed federated learning approach to limit the centralised server’s operating functionalities during the model training phase. Significantly adopting the federated learning mechanism helps to improve the overall data privacy in the transportation system. Notably, we used blockchain technology to ensure the authenticity and security of the aggregated training model. This paper examines typical attacks and demonstrates that the suggested solution preserves cooperative privacy for vehicular traffic systems while lowering computing costs for training the deep learning model to develop the autonomous, intelligent, distributed intrusion detection mechanism.

Index Terms—Blockchain, Federated Learning, Trustworthy, Vehicular Communication, Intrusion Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

The modern vehicular traffic system’s services primarily depend on the data collection process from the environment and the sharing of knowledge between different actors (e.g., pedestrians, vehicles, traffic administrators etc.). Notably, the emergence of autonomous and connected vehicles improves the quality of transportation services, and at the same time, it poses a massive challenge for effectively maintaining the traffic system by reducing accidents and enhancing safety and transportation convenience. Therefore, ensuring secure, reliable, and real-time communications between different actors and traffic management devices is necessary. However, Security and data privacy are the two crucial aspects of modern vehicular traffic system which need to be addressed before developing such communication networks.

Significantly, before securing the communication network, it is essential to know the different communication strategies which are involved in modern vehicular traffic network. The communication of vehicular traffic system can be classified into two following categories: (i.) *Vehicular communication* - it can be further classified into two parts; one is Inter-Vehicular communication, which stands for having the distribution of traffic and road conditions among vehicles in the range. There are also additional traffic management devices (e.g., Road-Side Units (RSU), traffic lights, surveillance cameras, etc.) and pedestrians from which vehicles can get information. The second one is Intra-Vehicular communication, which is a mechanism to communicate between Electronic Control Units (ECU), sensors and actuators of vehicles. These communication methodologies are mainly used to communicate sensor information and ECU messages along the vehicle. In addition, different communication buses are used for transferring ECU messages depending on functionality and speed. (ii.) *Infrastructure communication* - mainly stands for communicating between different traffic management devices (e.g., traffic lights, surveillance cameras, RSU), various authorities (e.g., traffic administrators, police, emergency rescue team, etc.) and pedestrians.

Secure and real-time communication between vehicles, traffic management devices and various authorities is essentially required. From the vehicle’s point of view, a cyber attacker can inject false and invalid traffic messages into the network to distract drivers from choosing a specific route or can use the network to determine a driver’s location or expose personal information. Even more, by gaining unauthorized access to the in-vehicle network, a cyber attacker can control a vehicle’s critical components, cause irreparable damage to the vehicle or its passengers, and even create a massive issue in the ongoing traffic system. In addition, it is also necessary to protect traffic management devices (e.g., RSU, traffic lights, surveillance cameras, etc.) from cyber threats and attacks to avoid any possible traffic collisions. Considering that fact, in this article, we have given our utmost focus to designing and building a secure, real-time and trustworthy vehicular traffic system. However, without developing an autonomous, distributed and intelligent attack and threat monitoring mechanism, it is not feasible to entirely secure the communication network and make it resilient. To address this issue, we propose an autonomous, intelligent and distributed intrusion detection

mechanism (AIDIDM) which can priorly detect malicious elements (e.g., attacked cars, compromised RSU or other traffic management devices) and activities. To develop the AIDIDM, it is necessary to reliably share the knowledge and data between different actors (e.g., vehicles, pedestrians, traffic administrators, etc.). To comply with current data privacy policies (e.g., GDPR), we have adopted the Federated Deep Learning technique to develop the AIDIDM. In addition, we integrated blockchain technology to bring trust between the various actors of our envisioned vehicular traffic system. Furthermore, blockchain technology has been used to prove the authenticity of the deep learning model that we have prepared for our AIDIDM, as well as to immutably maintain the reputations of the actors and traffic management devices without disclosing their sensitive and personal information.

The rest of this article is structured as follows. An overview of the related works and their research-technical gaps have been presented in the section II. In section III, by presenting the architectural framework of the modern vehicular traffic system, we proposed our AIDIDM for preventing potential cyber threats and attacks. Then, in section IV, we validate our proposal for using the federated deep learning technique to develop the AIDIDM. Finally, section V, presents the concluding remarks and future direction.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Many studies are currently being conducted to address the existing issues for preventing cyber attacks and threats in the modern vehicular network. In addition, many studies have been carried out in order to secure intra-vehicular and inter-vehicular communication. Many of these studies proposed various trustworthy and privacy-preserving communication and knowledge-sharing methodologies for developing a secure V2V communication channel by leveraging Blockchain facilities and Federated learning technologies [1], [2]. Notably, in the real world, in order to avoid hazards and accidents, it is necessary to ensure secure, trustworthy, and real-time communication between all traffic system actors (e.g., pedestrians, vehicles, cyclists, RSU, rescue teams, traffic administrators, and so on). Thus, each actor can securely exchange their knowledge and data based on the agreed governance rules and policies to develop a truly advanced, intelligent, resilient vehicular network. In order to develop this kind of network system, quite a few investigations have been done in vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I), vehicle-to-pedestrian (V2P), and vehicle-to-everything (V2X) domains [3]. Interestingly, developing this kind of network system not only helps to build an intelligent and autonomous traffic management system but also helps to promptly single out the compromised actors/devices and take the necessary procurement actions [4]. However, with the rising concern about global data privacy policies, it becomes more challenging to share the data and knowledge between different actors of the vehicular network. Therefore, we believe that the federated learning technique can play a crucial role in solving this issue.

Furthermore, adopting the federated learning technique would discard the necessity for sharing the raw data between different participants and reduce the network load, and

communication cost for the overall system [5]. Nonetheless, adopting the federated learning technique would pose a new challenge regarding the authenticity of the knowledge generators and other actors of the system. Thus, many researchers proposed integrating blockchain technology with the federated learning technique to solve this issue [6], [7]. Notably, blockchain technology's functionalities enable permanently storing the knowledge over the distributed ledger, helping to authenticate the knowledge-generator and store that information secretly without disclosing the sensitive and personal information of the actors. In our studies, we found that most of the researchers, given their concern about consolidating the data-privacy issues in the inter-vehicular or intra-vehicular network, while providing the solution to prevent the cyber-attacks and threats. However, as per our knowledge, we have not found any such proposal where researchers have presented a solution architecture for detecting the compromised participants or devices without disclosing the actors' sensitive information in advanced vehicular traffic networks.

III. PROPOSING SYSTEM MODEL

The main objective of this article is to design and develop the collaborative and intelligent intrusion detection methodology for building a secure and trustworthy vehicular traffic system. In order to fully understand the functions of the various involved system actors and components, we first visualised the overall architectural framework of the modern vehicular traffic system in this section. Then, we presented the mathematical solution for developing the collaborative deep learning-based intrusion detection model to develop an advanced and intelligent intrusion detection mechanism in modern vehicular networks and traffic systems. According to our investigation, several researchers have already used the convolutional neural network (CNN)-based deep learning technology to create intrusion detection systems for traffic and vehicular networks [8], [9], [10]. The main factor is that a CNN model needs much less training data compared to other deep learning models. In addition, it can train the model considerably faster than other deep learning models because it contains fewer parameters than any fully connected deep neural network. Similarly, here we also used the CNN-based deep learning model for autonomously detecting cyber threats and attacks.

A. Architectural description: Trustworthy Vehicular Network and Traffic System

These days, there are numerous types of vehicles on the road; some are fully autonomous (have autopilot), many are connected cars with advanced sensing devices and technologies, and there are also human-powered vehicles (e.g. bicycles). Besides all these vehicles, pedestrians are also one of the critical participants in any vehicular and traffic system. Notably, to avoid unnecessary circumstances (e.g., accidents) and maintain the flow of traffic, it is essential to develop an advanced traffic management system by integrating all the modern communication and computation technologies. Developing a secure, resilient, trustworthy, and real-time loop of communications between different actors (e.g. vehicles,

Fig. 1. Architectural framework: Advanced Vehicular traffic system

pedestrians, and traffic administrators) and traffic management devices (e.g., RSU, traffic lights, cameras) is essential to build in such kind of advanced vehicular traffic system.

Considering this requirement, this article depicts a three-layer functional architecture for an advanced vehicular network and traffic system, as shown in Fig. 1. The bottom layer of the architecture consists of vehicles, pedestrians and traffic management devices (e.g., RSUs, traffic lights, surveillance cameras, etc.). In our functional architecture, we named this architectural layer as *Terminal Access Layer*. Notably, vehicles, pedestrians, and traffic management devices (e.g., RSU, traffic lights, sensors, surveillance cameras) of *Terminal Access Layer* are responsible for producing a large amount of data and knowledge from various traffic and environmental events (e.g., vehicles activities, the traffic load, road conditions, weather conditions, etc.). Real-time processing of this vast amount of knowledge and data would help to develop an autonomous, secure and trustworthy vehicular traffic network. Furthermore, computation offloading from various actors (e.g., connected and autonomous cars, etc.) and traffic management devices (e.g., RSU, traffic lights, etc.) to servers in vehicular traffic systems is a critical matter for ensuring a high quality of Service (QoS) factor. Many researchers have proposed that the integration of edge and cloud computing can maximise communication and computation efficiency and also helps to maintain the high QoS factor in vehicular traffic systems [11], [12]. Thus, in our proposed architecture, we envisioned a combined and hierarchical *Cloud-Edge Computing Layer* on top of the *Terminal Access Layer* for aiming to move communication, computation and caching resources to close proximity of vehicles and pedestrians.

In addition, secure and efficient management and reliably exchanging this massive amount of knowledge and data between different actors are essentially required in the vehicular traffic system. To ensure that, we have adopted blockchain technology in our system. We developed the blockchain network over the cloud and edge servers in our proposed system. For convenience, we separated the computation-communication (*Cloud-Edge Computing Layer*) and knowledge-data storing (*Blockchain Network Layer*) lay-

ers in our proposed architectural diagram (Fig. 1). Notably, adding blockchain technology to our proposed architecture enables the opportunity to immutably maintain the reputations of the actors and traffic management devices without disclosing the actors' sensitive and personal information. Furthermore, adding blockchain technology to our proposed system facilitates the opportunity to authenticate the genuinity of produced knowledge and data along with their sources.

B. Mathematical Formulations: Development of the AIDIDM

Our primary goal is to develop secure, trustworthy, reliable, resilient and real-time communication between different actors, vehicles and traffic management devices. In order to achieve our primary goal, it is essential to develop an advanced and autonomous intrusion detection mechanism for monitoring the overall infrastructure to identify compromised actors, vehicles and traffic management devices and priorly take the necessary actions. Collecting massive event data from the transportation infrastructure is necessary to build that kind of intelligent intrusion detection mechanism. However, the rising concern about current data privacy policies (i.e., GDPR policy for connected vehicles and mobility related applications [13]) makes a massive challenge to collect data from various actors and vehicles. Therefore, in our proposal, we have integrated a fully distributed federated learning mechanism to develop an autonomous distributed intrusion detection mechanism. Federated learning (FL) is a distributed and advanced machine learning technique with high quality privacy protection. FL is highly secured in the sense that it requires the transference of model parameters rather than raw data between clients and the server. Generally, in FL we consider a system composing of K clients and a server \mathcal{K} , which cooperate to train a global optimal model w^* . In particular, each client holds a local dataset \mathcal{D}_k while the server does not hold any raw data. We describe the training process of FL in detail in the next paragraph. Notably, we have used the RSA cryptography mechanism for authenticating the clients, where we used the AES cryptography for encrypting the data and knowledge over the Blockchain network.

The server selects a subset of clients $\mathcal{K}_r \subseteq K$ on a random basis in each communication round r to send the current global

Algorithm 1 Global Deep learning Model Generation

Initial Consideration: $Accuracy = [\]$, K clients for generating global model (w^*), $(WA)_K^i$ is the corresponding unique wallet address for K_i client

Input: Distribution of Initial Global model (w^1), local datasets (\mathcal{D}_k)

Output: $Accuracy = [Acc_1, Acc_2, \dots, Acc_i, \dots, Acc_{m+1}]$

- 1: **FIRST PHASE:** Authentication of clients
- 2: **if** k_1 has $(WA)_K^1$ and authenticated by the Blockchain Network Layer **then**
- 3: **goto** SECOND PHASE;
- 4: **else**
- 5: Create an wallet and authenticate with Blockchain Network Layer
- 6: **end if**
- 7: **SECOND PHASE:**
- 8: **for** each $k \in K$ **do**
- 9: train received global copy of w^1 with \mathcal{D}_k by using SGD in each clients
- 10: Perform aggregation in Edge-Cloud server as follows:

$$w_{r+1} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_r} p_k w_{r+1}^k$$

- 11: Calculate $Accuracy_k$
 - 12: $Accuracy += Accuracy_k$
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: **return** w^* , $Accuracy_k$
-

w_r . Next, the selected clients use Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) to train the received global model w_r on their local dataset $\mathcal{D}_k = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_i, y_i)\}$. For the k -th client, the following objective function needs to be minimized:

$$\mathcal{L}_k(w) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_k|} \sum_{(x_i, y_i) \in \mathcal{D}_k} L_k(y_i, f_{w_k}(x_i)),$$

where $L_k(\cdot)$ is the cross-entropy function defined as:

$$L_k(y_i, f_{w_k}(x_i)) = y_i \log[f_{w_k}(x_i)] + (1 - y_i) \log[1 - f_{w_k}(x_i)],$$

y_i is the ground-truth of x_i and $f_{w_k}(\cdot)$ is the model-predicted probability vector. Here, the local update of the k -th client is as follows:

$$w_{r+1}^k = w_r - \eta \cdot \nabla \mathcal{L}_k(\mathcal{D}_k; w),$$

where η is the learning rate. Each client uploads its local model update w_{r+1}^k to the server after completing local training. Next, the server will aggregate all uploaded model updates into the current global model using the Federated Average Algorithm as follows:

$$w_{r+1} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_r} p_k w_{r+1}^k,$$

where $p_k = \frac{|\mathcal{D}_k|}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_r} |\mathcal{D}_k|}$ signifies the contribution rate of the k -th client to the current global model and \mathcal{K}_r represents the client set selected in the r -th round. It should be noted that in the entire FL training process, the model will tend to converge to obtain the optimal global model w^* with the number of

rounds increasing. A complete algorithmic step for global deep learning model generation has been presented in algorithm 1.

In our proposed solution, we integrated the convolutional neural network (CNN) as the base classifier algorithm and improved the intrusion detection effect for AIDIDM. The structure of the CNN design is illustrated in fig. 2. A CNN is a Deep Learning algorithm that involves the application of different models with convolutional layers, which determines inputs, features, classification, training and testing procedures. CNN is able to successfully seize the spatial and temporal

Fig. 2. Structural diagram of CNN

dependencies in an image through the application of relevant filters. Due to the reduction in the number of parameters involved and reusability of weights, the architecture performs a better fitting to the polytomous dataset (e.g., image dataset). The primary role of CNN is to reduce the images to a easily processable form, without losing features which are critical for achieving a good prediction. This is important when one needs to design an architecture which is not only good at learning but also scalable to massive datasets. The main task of the convolution layer is the extraction of high-level features from the input image. In general, CNN contains multiple convolution layers. The first convolution layer is essentially responsible for the extraction of low-level features such as edges, color, gradient orientation, etc. The architecture adapts to high-level features as well, providing us with a network that has excellent understanding of images in the dataset. Two types of results to the operation are possible, one in which the convolved feature is reduced in dimensionality compared to the input, and the other in which the dimensionality is either increased or remains same. The Pooling layer is responsible for reducing the spatial size of the convolved feature, similar to the convolution layer. This is done primarily to decrease the computational cost required to process the data through dimensionality reduction. Moreover, it is useful to extract dominant features which are invariant under rotation and translation, thereby maintaining the process of effectively training of the model. We use max pooling technique which returns the maximum value from the portion of the image covered by the convolution layer. It also performs as a Noise Suppressant, discarding the noisy activations altogether and de-noising along with dimensionality reduction. The convolution and pooling layers together form the k -th layer of a CNN for enabling the model to understand the features. Next, we flatten the final output and feed it to a regular Neural Network for classification purposes. A cheap way of learning non-linear combinations of the high-level features represented by the output of the convolutional layer is to add a Fully-Connected layer. The Fully-Connected layer is learning a nonlinear function in that space. We flatten the image into a column vector, given that

Fig. 3. Comparative measurement of loss function for six(6) different CNN models

we have converted our input image into a suitable form for our Multi-level Perceptron. The flattened output is fed to a feed-forward neural network and backpropagation applied to every iteration of training. The model is able to distinguish between high and low-level features in images and classify them using the Softmax function. In general, polytomous datasets are associated with vehicular network and traffic system. CNN is widely used in case of multilayered data as the number of parameters involved are less in comparison to other deep learning techniques and weights are reusable which helps the CNN architecture to perform a better fitting in our proposed AIDIM.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The main objective to perform the evaluation test is to find out the appropriate CNN model for developing our proposed AIDIM. Significantly, the performance of any CNN model cannot be interpreted visually and evaluation metrics are essential for the correct evaluation. The best evaluation metrics depend on the selected CNN algorithms, processed data and domain of application. The metrics are based upon the four

basic components of the confusion matrix which are – True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), True Negative (TN), False Negative (FN). Based on these four components of confusion matrix, the *Accuracy* of our proposed solution has been calculated as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$$

For conducting the test¹, we have used the cluster deployment of the FATE (Federated AI Technology Enabler) framework [14]. Our proposed AIDIM is evaluated on one benchmark vehicle network security dataset–CICIDS2017 [15]. To find the best CNN model for our proposed AIDIM, we have compared six (6) different and advanced CNN models, including VGG16, VGG19, Xception, Inception, Resnet, and InceptionResnet. Fig. 3 represents their loss function values during the training procedure. Notably, all six advanced CNN models performed very well on the provided data. For most of the CNN models, we found the training and testing accuracy is almost hundred percent, whereas the testing and training

¹Source code: https://github.com/Entice-HEU/intrusion_detection_BFL.git

Fig. 4. Comparative study: training and testing accuracy and training time for six advanced CNN models

accuracy of the Inception CNN model is marginally less than hundred percent. In contrast, the testing and training accuracy of the Resnet CNN model was considerably less than hundred percent. Considering the computational cost (i.e., in terms of training time of the model), we found that the VGG16 CNN took the least time to train the model, followed by Xception and VGG19 and so on, presented in Fig. 4. The main reason behind that, the normal and attack patterns in the considered dataset can properly be distinguished through the processed dataset. Following all the findings, we found that the VGG16 CNN model has the best-fitted CNN model for our proposed AIDIDM, followed by Xception and VGG19 CNN models.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Preventing cyber attacks and ensuring the highest level of data privacy is one of the primary concerns in the modern vehicular traffic system. In order to efficiently maintain the traffic flow, minimise any unnecessary hazards and improve transportation efficiency, each participant (e.g., vehicles, pedestrians, traffic administrators) needs to communicate with each other and exchange knowledge and data continuously. However, such communication facilities have introduced many security and privacy threats. This article primarily introduced a secure and trustworthy architectural framework for the modern vehicular traffic system to mitigate those threats and develop a reliable real-time communication network. Notably, we proposed and developed an autonomous, intelligent, distributed intrusion detection mechanism (AIDIDM) to make the system more resilient. We used the CNN deep learning model to bring intelligence to our proposed AIDIDM. Furthermore, we used the federated deep learning technique to train the model locally and ensure the modern data-privacy aspects. In addition, we adopted blockchain technology for immutably authenticating the trained model and authorising the system participants and traffic management devices. Finally, by performing some comparative tests and studies, we selected the suitable CNN model for developing the AIDIDM.

This work is presented as the initial study for making a secure and trustworthy vehicular traffic system. Notably, in this article, we have given major attention to finding the best-fit CNN model for developing the AIDIDM; therefore, the measurement of storing-time of data and knowledge and validating them over the blockchain network layer is out of the scope of this study. Along with this challenge, many other related challenges will be addressed in our future work.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work received partial funding from the projects DataCloud (H2020 101016835), and ONTOCHAIN (H2020 957338).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Otoum, I. Al Ridhawi, and H. T. Mouftah, "Blockchain-supported federated learning for trustworthy vehicular networks," in *GLOBECOM 2020-2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [2] S. R. Pokhrel and J. Choi, "Federated learning with blockchain for autonomous vehicles: Analysis and design challenges," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 68, no. 8, pp. 4734–4746, 2020.
- [3] P. K. Singh, S. K. Nandi, and S. Nandi, "A tutorial survey on vehicular communication state of the art, and future research directions," *Vehicular Communications*, vol. 18, p. 100164, 2019.
- [4] X. Sun, F. R. Yu, and P. Zhang, "A survey on cyber-security of connected and autonomous vehicles (cavs)," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2021.
- [5] S. R. Pokhrel and J. Choi, "A decentralized federated learning approach for connected autonomous vehicles," in *2020 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference Workshops (WCNCW)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [6] K. Toyoda, J. Zhao, A. N. S. Zhang, and P. T. Mathiopoulos, "Blockchain-enabled federated learning with mechanism design," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 219 744–219 756, 2020.
- [7] A. R. Javed, M. A. Hassan, F. Shahzad, W. Ahmed, S. Singh, T. Baker, and T. R. Gadekallu, "Integration of blockchain technology and federated learning in vehicular (iot) networks: A comprehensive survey," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 12, p. 4394, 2022.
- [8] A. R. Javed, S. Ur Rehman, M. U. Khan, M. Alazab, and T. Reddy, "Canintelliids: Detecting in-vehicle intrusion attacks on a controller area network using cnn and attention-based gru," *IEEE transactions on network science and engineering*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1456–1466, 2021.
- [9] M. D. Hossain, H. Inoue, H. Ochiai, D. Fall, and Y. Kadobayashi, "An effective in-vehicle can bus intrusion detection system using cnn deep learning approach," in *GLOBECOM 2020-2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [10] W. Lo, H. Alqahtani, K. Thakur, A. Almadhor, S. Chander, and G. Kumar, "A hybrid deep learning based intrusion detection system using spatial-temporal representation of in-vehicle network traffic," *Vehicular Communications*, vol. 35, p. 100471, 2022.
- [11] I. Sorkhoh, D. Ebrahimi, R. Atallah, and C. Assi, "Workload scheduling in vehicular networks with edge cloud capabilities," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 9, pp. 8472–8486, 2019.
- [12] J. Zhao, Q. Li, Y. Gong, and K. Zhang, "Computation offloading and resource allocation for cloud assisted mobile edge computing in vehicular networks," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 8, pp. 7944–7956, 2019.
- [13] E. D. P. Board, "Guidelines 1/2020 on processing personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility related applications," 2020.
- [14] Y. Liu, T. Fan, T. Chen, Q. Xu, and Q. Yang, "Fate: An industrial grade platform for collaborative learning with data protection." *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 22, no. 226, pp. 1–6, 2021.
- [15] I. Sharafaldin, A. H. Lashkari, and A. A. Ghorbani, "Toward generating a new intrusion detection dataset and intrusion traffic characterization." *ICISSP*, vol. 1, pp. 108–116, 2018.